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MEDICINAL SMALL-FLOWERED MOUNTAIN OREGANO (ORIGANUM TYTTANTHUM G.) RAW MATERIAL: PHYTOSCHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

*This study investigates the introduction of *Origanum tyttanthum* G. (small-flowered mountain oregano) under the ecological conditions of the Samarkand valley, focusing on the composition of its essential oil and pharmacological significance. The major bioactive compounds of the essential oil—carvacrol, γ -terpinene, *o*-cymene, β -caryophyllene, and α -terpineol—were analyzed. GC–MS analysis demonstrated that the phytochemical profile of the plant adapts to environmental conditions, and the introduction process contributes to an increase in the content of bioactive compounds. The results are significant for enhancing the quality of medicinal raw materials and for developing natural pharmaceutical products.*

Keywords: *Origanum tyttanthum, essential oil, carvacrol, introduction, phytochemistry, pharmacological significance.*

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing global demand for bioactive compounds obtained from medicinal plants as alternatives to synthetic substances. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 80% of the world population relies on plant-based natural preparations for the treatment of various diseases. [1].

From this perspective, plants of the Lamiaceae family, particularly species of the *Origanum* genus, hold significant importance in the pharmaceutical, food, perfumery, and cosmetic industries. Their essential oils are rich in biologically active compounds with antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antihistamine, and even anticancer properties. [2].

The bioactive compounds of medicinal plants are widely used in pharmaceuticals, traditional medicine, and the food industry, playing a crucial role in promoting human health. Studying their chemical composition and developing natural-based preparations, as well as enriching bioactive components through introduction, provides a scientific basis for further research. [3].

Origanum tyttanthum G. (small-flowered mountain oregano) is a medicinal plant belonging to the Lamiaceae family. Its essential oil contains bioactive compounds such as carvacrol (2-methyl-5-(methylethyl)phenol), γ -terpinene, o-cymene, β -caryophyllene, and α -terpineol, which exhibit anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial activity.

The ecological and climatic conditions of the Samarkand valley significantly influence the biochemical composition of plants. Therefore, studying the introduction of *O. tyttanthum* G. in this region and analyzing changes in its essential oil composition is both scientifically and practically relevant. [5].

Materials and Methods

The essential oils (EO) of *O. tyttanthum* G. strains AK-1 and AK-2M were obtained by hydrodistillation using a Clevenger apparatus at atmospheric pressure for

3 hours. The obtained distillate was extracted with n-hexane and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated to obtain pure essential oil.

The essential oil was stored at 4 °C in tightly sealed vials. The chemical composition of the essential oil was analyzed by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS). Analyses were performed using an Agilent 7890 GC chromatograph coupled with an Agilent 5975C Inert MSD mass spectrometer. Components were separated on an Agilent HP-INNOWax quartz capillary column. Mass spectra were compared with Wiley and NIST electronic libraries.

Results and Discussion

GC–MS analysis revealed that carvacrol was the major compound in the essential oil of *O. tyttanthum* G. introduced in the Samarkand valley. The main components of the essential oils of AK-1 and AK-2M strains are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Composition of AK-1 essential oil (GC–MS analysis)

No	Compound	RI	RT	Content, %
1	2-methyl-5-(methylethyl)phenol (Karvakrol)	2049	23.792	87.51
2	γ -Terpinene	1181	3.091	5.13
3	o-Cymene	1202	3.338	1.94
4	β -Caryophyllene	1521	10.728	1.37
5	α -Terpineol	1604	12.907	0.16
Total:				98,23

Table 2. Composition of AK-2M essential oil (GC–MS analysis)

No	Compound	RI	RT	Content, %
1	2-methyl-5-(methylethyl)phenol (Karvakrol)	2049	23.792	66.74
2	γ -Terpinene	1181	3.091	16.00
3	o-Cymene	1202	3.338	5.09
4	β -Caryophyllene	1521	10.728	3.28
5	α -Terpineol	1585	12.419	0.26
Total:				97.86

The presence of these compounds is characteristic of the *Origanum* genus, and variations in their quantity depend on environmental conditions and the plant's adaptive response. High concentrations of carvacrol and γ -terpinene enhance the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity of the essential oil. Furthermore, o-cymene and β -caryophyllene strengthen its antimicrobial properties.

The observed increase in carvacrol and γ -terpinene contents in AK-1 and AK-2M strains confirms the biochemical adaptation of the species to the Samarkand valley conditions.

Conclusion

GC–MS analysis conducted at the Samarkand University of Biotechnology laboratories demonstrated an increase in the content of major bioactive compounds in the essential oil of *O. yuttanthum* G. The carvacrol content reached 87.51% in the AK-1 strain and 66.74% in the AK-2M strain. Moreover, the increase in γ -terpinene (5.13–16.00%) and o-cymene (1.94–5.09%) enhanced the biological activity of the essential oil.

These results indicate that the introduction process is significant not only for environmental adaptation but also for enriching the phytochemical composition and improving the medicinal value of the plant.

Thus, introducing *O. yuttanthum* G. in the Samarkand valley can optimize the content of bioactive compounds, facilitate the cultivation of high-quality medicinal raw materials, and offer a promising direction for the pharmaceutical industry.

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